

MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ nanorods synthesized using NiO nanoparticles for hydrogen evolution in anion exchange membrane water electrolysis

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Abstract

The development of sustainable catalysts for anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers (AEMWE) has attracted considerable attention in recent years due to the possibility of using earth abundant elements to replace platinum group metals (e.g. Pt, Ru, Ir) as catalysts. One class of promising materials for the hydrogen evolution reaction are nickel-molybdenum compounds. Here we present a novel method for preparing Mo-Ni based catalysts with high dispersion using commercially available NiO nanoparticles as seeds. A complete physical and morphological characterization indicates that the NiO particles act as nucleation centers for the growth of NiMoO₄ nanorods. During high temperature reductive annealing, a MoO_{3-x} rich layer forms on the surface of the rods. Electrochemical measurements demonstrate enhanced performance when compared to the analogous material produced using Ni foam. The powder catalyst was applied to a membrane electrode assembly using a catalyst coated substrate technique and tests in AEMWEs were carried out with electrodes of 78.5 cm² area. A current density of 1 A cm² at a cell voltage of 1.8 V was obtained when coupled with an IrO₂ anode. When combined with a non PGM NiCo₂O₄ anode, 1 A cm² of electrolysis current density was produced at 2.0 V.

1. Introduction

Molecular hydrogen (H₂) is a promising energy vector that can be employed to store intermittent renewable energy through water electrolysis.[1] The current state of the art in water electrolysis is the proton exchange membrane water electrolyser (PEMWE). For PEM electrolyzers, the critical raw materials (CRMs) iridium, titanium and platinum are required to maintain stability due to the highly acidic environment created by the membrane.[2] The availability of CRMs will be crucial in the development of electrolyzer and fuel cell technologies for the hydrogen economy.[1] Operating an electrolyser with a membrane that transports anions (anion exchange membrane (AEM)), opens up the possibility of utilizing less expensive and more abundant materials. [3-6] A recent comparison of hydrogen production using AEM and PEM electrolysis showed that

both technologies have a similar life-cycle environmental profile.[7] AEM electrolysis shows significantly lower raw material criticality since it does not rely on platinum-group metals. Overall, a promising environmental and material criticality performance of AEM electrolysis for hydrogen production was concluded.[7] The performance of AEMWEs on a laboratory scale is promising [8] with current densities of up to 7.68 A cm^{-2} achieved at 2 V electrolyser voltage.[9] Regarding the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER), Pt/C remains the state-of-the-art cathode catalyst. Research into developing more sustainable HER electrocatalysts based on more abundant and cheaper elements is ongoing.[5] Examples are combinations of nickel and molybdenum that have been developed as alternatives to Pt.[10, 11] A number of different nanostructures and compositions have been reported.[12-15] Notably, high activity has been reported for catalysts based on $\text{MoNi}_4/\text{MoO}_{3-x}$ nanorod arrays.[16, 17] Previously, we have reported a HER catalyst composed of MoO_2 rich surface nanorods grown on Ni foam. The production of these standalone cathode electrodes was scaled to a 78.5 cm^2 surface area and they were employed in a 3-cell AEM electrolyser STACK.[18] The activity of this nickel foam based electrode is limited by the nature of the nickel foam support that allows only a small portion of the material to be coated with the active phase. Here we propose the advantages of a new strategy for preparing a Mo-Ni powder catalyst composed solely of the nanorod particles, using commercially available NiO nanopowder as substrate thus avoiding the need for nickel foam. NiO nanoparticles are used as a “seed” on which NiMo structures can grow. A complete physical (HR-TEM, SEM, XPS, Raman) and electrochemical characterization is reported. In-situ and ex-situ Raman spectroscopy indicate the formation of a surface rich in MoO_{3-x} active phases. We then applied the catalyst powder to an 78.5 cm^2 MEA using a catalyst coated substrate technique and we tested the electrodes in a single cell AEMWE. At a current density of 1 A cm^2 , the stable cell voltage was 1.8 V with an IrO_2 anode and 2.0 V with a NiCo_2O_4 anode compared to 0.5 A cm^2 at 1.85 V using the nickel foam supported catalyst reported in our previous paper.

2. Experimental section

All metal salts and reagents were purchased from Merck and used as received. All the solutions were freshly prepared with doubly distilled deionized water. The fumasep FAA-3-PK130 membrane and ionomer FAA-3-FILM were purchased from Fumatech GmbH (Germany).

2.1 Catalyst synthesis

The catalyst powder $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ was prepared using a two-step synthesis. Firstly, 1.2 mmol of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.3 mmol of $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed together with 100 mg of NiO nanopowder 98.8 % (particle size $<50 \text{ nm}$ (TEM)) in 60 ml of distilled water. The solution was then sonicated for 30 mins to help suspend the NiO nanopowder. The black suspension was sealed inside a PTFE lined autoclave and heated at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 h. The resulting yellow precipitate denoted as (NiMoO_4) was then filtered, washed with water and dried at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Finally, the MoNiO_4 precursor was placed inside a rotating quartz oven (Carbolyte Gero TSO 11/400), purged for 30 minutes with N_2 then heated to either 500 or 600 $^\circ\text{C}$ at $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ for 2 hours under a flow of the gas mixture $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2$ (5:95, v/v) with a flow rate of 0.5 slm; the furnace was then cooled down to room temperature with a 3°C min^{-1} ramp. Two samples were prepared using two temperatures at 500 and 600 $^\circ\text{C}$. Each sample is denoted using the preparation temperature.

2.2 Physical characterization

SEM and EDX sample characterization studies were performed using a TESCAN Gaia 3 FIB/SEM. The microscope hosts a 30 kV Triglav electron column and a Cobra focused gallium ion beam column. SEM images

of the sample surfaces were acquired using two in-beam secondary electron (SE) and back scattered electron (BSE) detectors. EDX maps on the cross-sections were acquired by using the instrument EDAX HI-OCTANE detector. TEM and elemental mapping were performed employing a Talos™ F200X G2 TEM microscope (Thermo Scientific). Samples were prepared by suspending 1-2 mg of sample in 1 mL of isopropanol (ACS reagent, ≥99.5% from Sigma Aldrich). The samples were sonicated for about 20 min. A drop of the suspension was then drop casted on a Holey TEM Copper grid, which was used as a sample holder for the characterization. XRD analysis was carried out using X'Pert PRO device (PANalytical) equipped with Co anode (wavelength K- α 1 1.78901 Å). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were carried out in a UHV chamber with a base pressure lower than 10⁻⁹ mbar. The chamber was equipped with non-monochromatized Al radiation ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) and a hemispherical electron energy analyzer (VSW with a 16-channel detector). The operating power of the X-ray source was 150 W (15 kV and 10 mA) and photoelectrons were collected normal to the sample surface, maintaining the analyzer angle between the analyzer axis and X-ray source fixed at 54.5°. All the samples were fixed on carbon tape and XPS spectra were acquired in a fixed analyzer transmission mode with a fixed pass energy of 44.0 eV. The spectra were analyzed by using the CasaXPS software. Linear or Shirley functions have been used to subtract the background. The de-convolution of the XPS spectra has been carried out by applying a combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions (70/30-ratio) and a Lorentzian Asymmetric function, depending on the element. Binding energies (B.E.) were calibrated upon fixing the C 1s component of the carbon tape at 285.1 eV. [19] The ex-situ Raman spectra were obtained with a Renishaw Raman spectrometer with a grating of 2400 grooves/mm in backscattering geometry with a 514 nm laser excitation wavelength. For the in-situ reduction, the precursor NiMoO₄/NiO was placed in a high temperature Linkam stage (TS1200) at a set temperature of 630°C under a 5% H₂ 95% N₂ atmosphere. The Raman spectra of the reduced catalysts were measured on an in Via Renishaw Raman spectrometer with a 785 nm laser excitation wavelength and a grating of 1200 grooves/cm at 5% laser power, corresponding to approximately 250 μ W.

2.3 Electrochemical measurements

All the glassware was cleaned with a H₂O₂/H₂SO₄ conc. solution overnight and rinsed several times with Milli-Q water before use. Milli-Q water was used to prepare the KOH 0.1 M solution, that was purged with N₂ or H₂, for 30 minutes before the tests (all measurements were conducted under gas bubbling). Catalyst inks were composed of 5.8 mg mL⁻¹ catalyst powder in 50:50 (v/v) water/ethanol containing 1 wt % of Nafion 5w%. The resulting suspension was sonicated (59 Hz, 100 W) for 30 min. Electrochemical tests were conducted in a typical three-electrode system. The working electrode was prepared by drop-casting the ink suspension onto the glassy carbon area of the rotating disk electrode (RDE). The metal loading was determined by weighing the amount of the dry deposit on the glassy carbon (area = 0.1964 cm²). A standard Ag/AgCl sat. electrode and Au wire were used as the reference and counter electrodes respectively. The cell potential was referenced to RHE by adding 0.964 V (0.197 + 0.059 × pH). All potentials were corrected electrolyte resistance and all measurements were performed at 25 °C.

Electrochemical tests were carried out using a Parstat 2273 (Princeton Applied Research), data were collected with the software "PowerSuit". Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and hydrogen oxidation reaction (HOR) polarization curves were evaluated by performing scans between -0.2 and 0.2 V vs. RHE at 1 mV s⁻¹, keeping the rotation speed of the RDE at 1600 rpm. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out in a 0.1 M KOH solution, under an N₂ atmosphere (after 30 minutes of N₂ purge), with a frequency range spanning from 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz, at a potential of 100 mV. The data and the equivalent circuit were elaborated with "Zwiev4" and "EC lab" software. The double-layer capacitances (C_{dl}) were measured, by conducting cyclic voltammetry in 1.0 M KOH with different scan rates from 20 to 100 mV s⁻¹ in a potential window of 0.514 to 0.614 V (vs. RHE). The capacitor charging current j_c and discharging current j_a

at 0.564 V were plotted versus the scan rate v according to the equation: $|j| = v \times Cdl$, where Cdl is the slope of the linear fit.

2.4 AEM water electrolysis cell testing

The $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode coated electrode was prepared by mixing 100 mg of catalyst powder with 100 mg aqueous PTFE suspension (10wt%), and 60 mg Vulcan XC-72 carbon, a few drops of distilled water were added and mixed with the slurry until a fine paste is obtained. The paste was uniformly coated onto 5 cm^2 of Ni foam (Alantum Europe GmbH Germany – pore size 450 μm , AD 420 g m^{-2} , Thickness 1.5 mm). The electrode was then wet proofed at 350 °C for 15 minutes under N_2 flow.

Membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs), with the 5 cm^2 cathode and nickel foam anode electrodes were assembled together with a FAA-3-PK-130 membrane (Fumatech) using appropriate gaskets and graphite plate (cathode) and steel plate (anode) using a stainless-steel Scribner test cell (Scribner Corp. USA). A 4 Nm torque closing force was used. The AEM was pre-activated by feeding the cells with KOH 1 M for 12 hours at 60 °C before each experiment. An 8 channel Arbin LBT21084 battery test station (Arbin Instrument) potentiostat/galvanostat was used to control the electrolysis cell; a peristaltic pump (Gilson Mini Pulse) was used to feed the electrolyser with an aqueous solution of KOH (1 M) at the anode with a 1 ml min^{-1} flow rate, while no solution was fed to the cathode. The cathode compartment was connected to a Bronkhorst ELFlow flow meter in order to quantify the H_2 produced by the cell. Scan voltage curves were acquired between 0 and 2 V at a 10 mV s^{-1} scan rate. Galvanostatic experiments were performed by applying a constant current load of 1 A cm^{-2} to the cell while monitoring the cell voltage. The internal ohmic resistance was estimated using an external potentiometer, connected to the heads of the cell. All experiments were performed with the cell heated at 60 °C.

2.5 Scale up and electrolysis cell testing

2.5.1 Catalyst ink preparation: The $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C catalyst was mixed homogeneously with Vulcan XC-72 carbon at a ratio of 1:0.6 using ball milling. The catalyst ink was prepared by mixing the catalyst powder with chloromethylated poly(styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene) block copolymer (PSEBS-CM) acting as the polymer binder of the catalyst layer. The catalyst to binder ratio (wt.%) was 90:10. Chloroform was used as dispersant of the catalyst particles and polymer binder solvent.

2.5.2 Electrode preparation: Membrane-electrode assemblies (MEA) were prepared using a catalyst coated substrate method. The catalyst layer was deposited on the surface of the Ni foam by sonicated dispersion deposition method. Electrodes of geometrical area 78.5 cm^2 (circle of 10 cm diameter) were prepared. The catalyst loading was 5 mg cm^{-2} . After the deposition of the catalyst layer, electrodes were immersed in 10 wt.% DABCO (1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane) solution at room temperature for 48 hours in order to introduce DABCO functional groups to the PSEBS-CM.[20] After activation, the electrodes were immersed in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH solution to change the polymer binder to the OH^- form. Ni foam coated with IrO_2 (2 mg cm^{-2}) and NiCo_2O_4 spinel oxide catalysts (5 $\text{mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2}$) using the same technique were used as anode electrodes.

2.5.3 Alkaline water electrolysis testing: A laboratory alkaline water electrolysis cell with active area of 78.5 cm^2 was used to evaluate the electrochemical behaviour of the prepared electrodes. Modulab potentiostat (Ametek) with 100 A booster were used for electrochemical measurements. Anion exchange polymer membrane PSEBS-CM-DABCO (thickness in dry state 60 μm) was used as membrane between anode and cathode. The concentration of the liquid electrolyte was 1 M KOH at a temperature of 50 °C. The activation of the electrodes was done by potentiostatic measurement at constant cell voltage 1.9 V for NiCo_2O_4 anode and at 1.6 V for IrO_2 anode electrode respectively for 15 hours. Values of the cell voltage were chosen to achieve similar initial current density. After the activation procedure, the short-term measurement of the load

curves followed in cell voltage range 1.5–2.0 V. Cell voltage increase was step-wise with step 0.05 V. Each point was measured for 60 seconds in order to reach steady state and between each point the cell was polarized by voltage of 1.2 V for 60 seconds to remove the produced bubbles. The load curve measurement was accompanied by measurement of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy at cell voltages in the range from 1.3–1.8 V in the case of NiCo₂O₄ anode and in the range of 1.2–1.6 V in the case of IrO₂ anode. The amplitude was 10 mV and the frequency range was 100 kHz–0.1 Hz. The resistances were evaluated using equivalent electrical circuit shown in Figure S1. Due to the absence of the second time constant with NiCo₂O₄ anode, simplified equivalent electrical circuit missing R3 and CPE2 elements was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Synthesis and characterization:

A commercial NiO nanopowder was used as substrate for the growth of NiMoO₄ nanorods using a hydrothermal synthesis in aqueous solution (150 °C for 6 h). This was followed by reductive annealing at high temperature (2 samples prepared at 500 and 600 °C respectively) under a flow of 5% H₂/N₂ gas mixture. ICP-OES analysis of the as-formed NiMoO₄ nanorods gave Mo 38.9 wt% and Ni 27.4 wt% (33.7 wt% O), while for MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C) gave Mo 49.6 wt% and Ni 35.2 wt% (14.8 wt% O). We have already demonstrated that in this temperature range (500–600 °C) the most active materials are formed for the nickel foam supported material.[18] During the annealing treatment under reducing atmosphere, the rod-shape structure is maintained, while the surface undergoes morphological and phase transformation. SEM images of the samples after synthesis confirm the rod structures and show how the starting NiMoO₄ develops a rougher surface as the high temperature reductive annealing treatment proceeds, with the formation of surface agglomerates and nanoparticles (Figures 1a and 1b). The sample prepared at 600 °C has a visibly rougher surface than that formed at 500 °C. The formation of the typical rod-structure is also confirmed by TEM analysis (Figure 2). The TEM image in Figure 2a shows the formation of highly crystalline MoNiO₄ rods formed during the hydrothermal synthesis and prior to the reductive annealing step. The NiO nanoparticles used as substrate for the synthesis are visible, embedded on the surface of the rod structures (see Figure S2). XRD analysis of the powder indicates the formation of NiMoO₄. [21] Interestingly, the hydrothermal synthesis was not successful in the absence of the NiO nano powder. Previously, we have reported the growth of NiMoO₄ rods on a nickel foam substrate.[18]

Figure 1: SEM images of a) MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 500°C and b) MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600°C

Figure S3 shows clearly how the smooth surface of the MoNiO_4 rods decomposes and transforms into a sponge-like structure after thermal annealing. Rather than forming a thin coating on the solid nickel foam substrate, the NiO seeded catalyst is a homogeneous nano powder composed of small-roughened rods. TEM images and elemental mapping reveal structural rearrangements and changes in the distribution of species. **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**a shows a TEM image of NiMoO_4 , which shows high crystallinity and the presence of the NiO nanopowder, which is proved by elemental distribution in Figure S2. After the heat treatment at 500 or 600 °C a general roughening is observed for both samples. From elemental mapping, it can be seen that Mo tends to distribute homogeneously and even after the thermal treatments it appears well-dispersed (**Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**d and **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**h), while XPS shows an increase in Mo surface concentration (Table 1). **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**c shows that Ni is less homogeneously dispersed on the surface, an effect that increases as the temperature rises (**Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**g). The NiO particles on the surface are reduced to Ni metal and combine with Ni from the precursor to form larger Ni particles,[22] forming seemingly crystalline structures as demonstrated by TEM bright field imaging in Figure S4. These observations confirm that the reductive annealing causes a phase transition and the segregation of Mo to the surface. The XPS and Raman (Section 3.2) investigations point to the formation of a surface rich in MoO_{3-x} . This structure was also found to form on nickel foam supported Ni-Mo, which has undergone the same synthetic treatment.[18]

Figure 2: a) TEM image of precursor NiMoO_4 . b-e) STEM images and elemental mapping of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500°C), and f-i) STEM images and elemental mapping of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C).

The surface chemical composition of these materials was investigated by XPS (**Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**). The high-resolution Mo 3d signal is deconvoluted into four components at 227.9, 229.2, 230.4, and 232.2 eV corresponding to Mo(0), Mo(IV), Mo(V), and Mo(VI), respectively. The surface of the precursor NiMoO_4 is characterized by a mixture of Mo and Ni, with Mo present in the (VI) oxidation state. Nickel exists mostly in the oxidized form, with a small amount of Ni(0) present. These spectra correspond to the expected species NiMoO_4 . After high temperature reductive annealing, NiMoO_4 undergoes a process of dehydration and partial decomposition to form surface species such as MoO_2 and MoO_3 . Both samples at 500°C and 600°C clearly show a significant lowering of the amount of Mo(VI) and at the same time an increase of Mo(IV) and Mo(V) signals. At 600 °C the presence of Mo(IV) is 36 %, implying the formation of a MoO_2 phase which is in accordance with the catalytic performance, as MoO_2 represents the main active species for the hydrogen evolution reaction. These spectroscopic results are consistent with the surface NiMoO_4 being partially reduced to MoO_2 .[19, 23] XPS analysis also shows that the percentage of Mo on the surface increases (see tables S1, S2, S3) after the annealing treatments, in agreement with the previous work, in which a migration of Mo species occurred under the same conditions.[18] Nevertheless, a discrepancy emerges if we compare the formation of the different Mo oxidation states with the ones of the nickel foam supported catalysts. From Table S4 it is clear that Mo in $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ is more oxidized, with Mo(VI) at 60 % compared to 3% for the Nickel foam material. Mo(V) remain quite similar especially for MoO_2/NiO 600 °C. It is interesting to note that

Mo(IV) is present to a lesser extent for powder catalyst as well as metal Mo (Mo(0)) (Table S4). Regarding Ni, the metallic phase increases after heat treatment and was found to be more abundant in the 600 °C specimen (Figure 3). The relative concentrations are listed in the Supporting Information (Tables S1, S2, S3). The reduction of the NiO nanoparticles to Ni metal occurs during reductive annealing so the presence of metallic nickel is not due to NiMo alloy formation as no metallic Mo is observed.

Figure 3: XPS spectra of Mo and Ni for a-b) NiMoO₄ precursor, c-d) MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 500 °C, e-f) MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600 °C.

Table 1: Molybdenum surface composition (%) for each sample by XPS.

	NiMoO ₄	MoO _{3-x} NiMoO ₄ (500 °C)	MoO _{3-x} NiMoO ₄ (600 °C)
Mo element percentage	9.3	10.1	10.9

3.2 In-situ Raman spectroscopy

In situ and ex situ Raman spectroscopy was used to probe the surface structural changes occurring during synthesis. The ex-situ room temperature Raman spectrum of the NiMoO₄ precursor is plotted in Figure 4a. Clear Raman features are observed in the regions between 320–400 cm⁻¹ and 770–980 cm⁻¹. NiMoO₄ exhibits polymorphism (α and β forms), β is the high temperature form with Mo in the tetrahedral environment.[24] The α form has Mo in the octahedral coordination, which exhibits characteristic Raman vibrations around 700 cm⁻¹. [25] Such a signature is clearly missing from the Raman spectrum indicating an absence of this phase in the material. Given the relatively low temperature synthesis and the instability of the β form at low temperatures, we predict that the precursor is in the hydrated phase of nickel molybdate (NiMoO₄·nH₂O). This is in agreement with various Raman studies of hydrated nickel molybdate, which exhibit high intensity modes around 356, 828, 870 and 947 cm⁻¹. [26] These modes correspond to the tetrahedral coordination of Mo that both NiMoO₄·nH₂O and β -NiMoO₄ have in common. Modes below 400 cm⁻¹ correspond to molybdenum-oxygen bending and the frequencies above 770 cm⁻¹ to stretching, while the intense mode at 948 cm⁻¹ is the symmetrical Mo-O stretching vibration.[27]

Figure 4: a) Room temperature Raman spectrum of the NiMoO₄ precursor. b) Spectra of the NiMoO₄ precursor as a function of temperature.

It has been previously reported that heating hydrated nickel molybdate results in its transformation into the α form or beta form round 400 °C.[28] We do not observe any new vibrational bands in the 700 cm⁻¹ region with increasing temperature, Figure 4b, indicating the absence of the α form. Around 500 °C the mode at 871 cm⁻¹ disappears and a new mode at 881 cm⁻¹ appears. This is similar to the spectra of β -NiMoO₄, which have been reported to have intense modes around 890 cm⁻¹. [25] Additionally, the intensity of the 356 mode shifts to 380 cm⁻¹ around 500 °C. Bankar et al. measured the Mo-O bending mode in beta NiMoO₄ at 371 cm⁻¹, which is also upshifted in comparison to the hydrated NiMoO₄. [29] We therefore conclude that the NiMoO₄·*n*H₂O transforms from the hydrated to the β form at around 500°C.

The reduction of the precursor using in situ Raman spectroscopy is depicted in Figure 5. The sample was heated in air to a set point of 630 °C when the 5% H₂ 95% N₂ gas was purged through the stage and Raman spectra were measured as a function of time. The NiMoO₄ precursor modes are visible until about 20 minutes into the reduction, upon which they abruptly disappear, Figure 5a. The intensities of the spectra in Figure 5a are normalized in order to visualize the very low intensity spectra of the reduced sample. The intensities of the precursor modes, Figure 5b, decrease with reduction time signifying the reduced amount of the NiMoO₄ phase in the sample during reduction. However, the NiMoO₄ Raman peak positions remain constant, Figure 5c. Usually, introduction of oxygen vacancies in metal oxides shifts their vibrational modes to lower frequencies as their bonds expand upon reduction. [30] Previous studies using in situ XRD and Raman during the reduction of α -NiMoO₄ did not find evidence of intermediate NiMoO_{4-x} suboxides. [31, 32] This corroborates our results, that the reduction of NiMoO₄ results in a phase change rather than the accommodation of oxygen vacancies to form NiMoO_{4-x}. Rodriguez et al. suggested based on in situ XRD and XANES, that a rapid surface reduction of α -NiMoO₄ occurs above 325 °C, while reduction to metallic Mo proceeds only above 725 °C under hydrogen atmosphere. [31] These results are in good agreement with our measurements. The rapid reduction after 20 minutes changes the surface color of the sample to black, which absorbs the Raman laser that cannot penetrate deeper into the sample.

To assign the phase of the reduced precursor, we measured Raman spectra of the catalysts reduced at 500 °C and 600 °C, Figure 6. The spectra were taken with a Raman laser excitation wavelength of 785 nm, in order to increase the penetration depth of the dark samples. The laser energy was kept around 250 μ W in order to

prevent sample heating that could lead to a reduction or oxidation of the material. In both spectra, we identify the remains of the NiMoO_4 precursor at frequencies above 850 cm^{-1} . Further we observe weak Raman modes around 189 , 340 , 714 and 815 cm^{-1} , Figure 6. These agree with spectra of sub-oxides between MoO_3 and MoO_2 , referenced here as MoO_{3-x} . [33] The mode around 814 cm^{-1} is a signature of the MoO_3 phase, meaning that the Mo^{6+} oxidation state is present in the catalysts in the form of both MoO_3 and NiMoO_4 . In conclusion, Raman predicts that the reduced catalyst contains remains of the NiMoO_4 precursor as well as suboxides of MoO_{3-x} , which is in good agreement with the XPS measurements.

Figure 5: a) In-situ Raman spectroscopy of the reduction of NiMoO_4 . Temperature set at $630\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Atmosphere switched to $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2$ mix at $T=0$. The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity and their intensity is normalized to their maximum intensity. Intensities b) and positions c) of the NiMoO_4 stretching modes as a function of reduction time.

Figure 6: Raman spectra of the catalysts reduced at 500°C and 600°C, with reference to MoO₂ and MoO_{3-x}. [33]

3.3 Electrochemical characterization

The activity for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) was evaluated for both the samples MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ prepared at 500 and 600 °C, and also for a commercial Pt(40%)/C as benchmark catalyst. In **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**, linear scan voltammeteries (LSV) are reported for the MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ samples. The material prepared at 600 °C shows the best performance in terms of mass activity and specific activity compared to MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 500 °C (Table 2). Electrochemical capacitance measurements are shown in Figure 7c–d. An increase in the Cdl from 0.63 to 0.71 mF cm⁻² occurs when the annealing temperature is increased from 500 to 600 °C. And, as stated before, a general Mo surface enrichment (Table 1), with the formation of more Mo⁴⁺ species at 600 °C (Figure 3), and homogenous presence of oxide species in TEM micrographs (**Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**) prove that Mo is distributed uniformly. Catalytic activity cannot be explained by the presence of NiMo-alloys, as no trace of Mo(0) signal in the XPS spectra was found, this is accordance with the difficulty in reducing molybdenum at temperatures under 600 °C. [34, 35] Increased activity can be explained by the increased surface area, and by the enhanced phase separation of MoO_{3-x} to the surface that occurs during heat treatment at 600 °C [36] and also to the presence of Ni/NiO interface that favors the Volmer–Heyrovsky or Volmer–Tafel processes. [37] Tafel analysis was also carried out for a more quantitative evaluation of the LSV data. The linear fitting of log J vs η curves are directly reported with respective Tafel slopes values in **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.** MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C), exhibits a lower Tafel slope for the HER compared to MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (500 °C), and also a higher value of exchange current density for MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C) 3.24 A g_{Metal}⁻¹ (see Table 2), which reflect the improved activity compared to MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (500°C). A direct comparison of the HER activity between MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C) and the analogous material prepared on nickel foam (Figure S6) confirms the advantage of the synthesis using NiO as seed material compared to the Nickel foam approach, showing an increase in specific activity of 2.06 mA cm² @ -0.1 V vs RHE (Figure S6). Impedance measurements were also recorded for MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ at 500 and 600 °C (Figure 7e-f): EIS data were collected at open circuit potential (OCP) and in the region of the faradaic process of hydrogen evolution, at -0.1 V vs RHE. In the first case, Nyquist plot (Figure 7e) shows high polarization resistance, which makes it difficult to recognize at low frequency the straight line at 45° typical of the diffusive phenomena described by Warburg element. In the HER region (Figure 7f) instead, a semicircle at low frequency is observed for both samples, from here the value of charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) was obtained. For MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 500 °C, R_{ct} is higher compared to MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600 °C, 420 Ω and 134 Ω respectively. The R_{ct} value lowers and the activity rises, as pointed out by the polarization curve experiments. It is

noteworthy that performing EIS at a lower potential of -0.05 V vs RHE, leads to an increase of the Rct values in both cases (Figure S7). For $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C the first semicircle at high frequency is not affected by the change in potential but only the one at low frequency (see Figure S7), due to the fact that reaction kinetics are affected by the overpotential, it can be stated that semicircle at high frequencies is not related to the kinetics of the reaction.[38, 39]

Figure 7: LSVs from HER to HOR region of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 and 600 °C, 1 mV s^{-1} at 1600 rpm rotating disk. Inset shows the comparison in the HOR region. b) Tafel plots with relative Tafel slope for HER and HOR. Cdl measurement for c) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C and d) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C. CVs recorded in the potential windows of 0.514 – 0.614 V vs. RHE with no faradaic processes. Cdl (Capacitance double layer) were obtained by the slope of the capacitive current determined at 0.56 V as a function of scan rate (see insets). Nyquist plot obtained from impedance measurements at open circuit value a), and b) in HER region at -0.1 V vs RHE.

Table 2: Important electrochemical parameters extrapolated from LSV analysis.

	Specific activity $[[\text{mA cm}^{-2}]]$ @ $\eta = 0.1$ V		Mass activity $[[\text{A g}_{\text{Metal}}^{-1}]]$ @ $\eta = 0.1$ V		Exchange current $[\text{A g}_{\text{Metal}}^{-1}]$	Tafel slope $[\text{mV dec}^{-1}]$	
	HOR	HER	HOR	HER		HOR	HER
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C	0.07	0.11	0.48	0.76	0.30	169	139.2
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C	0.61	2.60	4.16	17.64	3.24	118.2	75
Pt(40%)/C	3.11	25.8	32.88	272.32	16.45	74.6	43.1

AEM water electrolysis cell testing

The electrolysis cell was evaluated through polarization curves from 0 to 2 V at 10 mV s^{-1} . The cell temperature was controlled at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A typical polarization curve (Figure 8a) shows a large improvement compared to the MoO_2 on Ni foam cathode, reaching 820 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V (550 mA cm^{-2} for the catalyst grown on Ni foam).[18] Stability was also evaluated by running the cell for 50 hours at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a current load of 1 A cm^{-2} . In Figure 8b the trend of the curve shows clearly how the stability is maintained after each replacement of fresh KOH solution. During the test the cell voltage oscillated around 2.2 V with a cell voltage-based energy cost of $57.7 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2$. The MoO_2 on Ni foam cathode under the same conditions maintained stable operation at around 1.85 V at 0.5 A cm^{-2} . [18]

Figure 8: a) Typical polarization curve for the AEM electrolysis cell at 60°C , b) cell voltage monitored at 1 A cm^{-2} . AEMWE with $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ cathode and Ni foam anode with Fumatech FAA-3-PK-130 AEM.

3.4 AEM scale-up electrode testing

Membrane-electrode assemblies (MEA) with an active area of 78.5 cm^2 were prepared using a catalyst coated substrate method. The catalyst layer, which is a mixture of catalyst particles and Vulcan-XC72 powder prepared by ball milling, was deposited on the surface of Ni foam by sonicated dispersion deposition method. Electrodes of geometrical area 78.5 cm^2 (10 cm diameter disks) were prepared with a catalyst loading of 5 mg cm^{-2} . The same method was used to prepare two types of anode electrodes; Ni foam coated with IrO_2 (2 mg cm^{-2}) and with NiCo_2O_4 spinel oxide catalysts ($5 \text{ mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The catalyst layer contains a poly(styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene) block copolymer (PSEBS-CM) acting as the polymer binder. The polymer also acts as anion conductor after treatment of the preformed electrode with DABCO that adds quaternary ammonium groups along the polymer chains that favour anion transport. Cathode and anode electrodes were assembled within the electrolysis cell hardware with an anion exchange polymer membrane PSEBS-CM-DABCO (thickness in dry state $60 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). The cell temperature was $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 1 M aqueous KOH was fed to both anode and cathode compartments. The procedure used to obtain the load curves shown in Figure 9 is described in the experimental section. Figure 9 shows the cell voltage versus current density curves for the cells with a PGM anode (IrO_2) and a non PGM anode (NiCo_2O_4). It is clear that the cell with IrO_2 anode outperforms the NiCo_2O_4 anode, achieving 0.9 A cm^{-2} at cell voltage 1.8 V. The same current density of 0.9 A cm^{-2} was achieved at 2.0 V using a non PGM NiCo_2O_4 anode catalyst. In our previous report, the nickel foam supported catalyst was also applied in the same up-scaled cell under similar conditions combined with a nickel foam connected as anode electrode. The cell reached 0.23 A cm^{-2} at 1.8 V. At 0.2 A cm^{-2} the cell operated at a stable voltage

of 1.95 V over 60 h. These results confirm the advantage of catalysing the cathode electrode with the $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C powder compared to cathodes prepared by the growth of MoNi structures on the nickel foam structure.

Figure 9: Load curves of the alkaline water electrolysis with $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode and anodes using IrO_2 and NiCo_2O_4 catalyst. Temperature 50 °C, 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, PSEBS-CM-DABCO (60 μm thick) separator, 2 mg $\text{IrO}_2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, 5 mg $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, geometrical is 78.5 cm^2 .

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was used in order to obtain further insight into the performance of the tested electrodes. Values of ohmic (R_s) and polarisation resistances (R_p) evaluated from the measured spectra are shown in **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů..**

Figure 10: Results of ohmic resistance (a) (R_s) and (b) polarisation resistances (R_p) evaluated from EIS spectra. Temperature 50 °C, 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, PSEBS-CM-DABCO (60 μm thick) separator, 2 mg $\text{IrO}_2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, 5 mg $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode, geometrical are 78.5 cm^2 . EIS measured in the frequency range 100 kHz–10Hz, with maximal amplitude 10 mV.

Figure 10a shows that the cell with the IrO_2 based anode has a R_s 7% lower than the NiCo_2O_4 cell. This small difference may be explained by higher electric conductivity of catalyst layer composed of IrO_2 catalyst when compared to catalyst layer utilizing NiCo_2O_4 . A more significant difference was observed for R_p values shown in Figure 10b, which can be attributed to the reaction rate at the electrode surfaces. In the case of the NiCo_2O_4 catalyst only one semicircle is observed (Figure S10b), while in the case of the IrO_2 catalyst, two semicircles are visible (Figure S10a).

Due to slower kinetics and four-electron transfer (compared to two-electron HER), the R_p value of $1.51 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for NiCo_2O_4 catalyst was assigned to the OER reaction. In the case of the IrO_2 catalyst the two values of R_p are observed (0.13 and $0.04 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ respectively). These results indicate that the application of the non-PGM catalyst for OER was the limiting factor in the cell performance with a very high R_p values. On the other hand, the application of the more active IrO_2 catalyst resulted in decrease of the OER polarisation resistance to the extent that the effect of the cathode electrode resistance becomes observable in the EIS analysis. Lower polarisation resistance for the OER using the highly active IrO_2 catalyst accounts for the difference in cell performance and highlights the need for the development of highly active non PGM OER catalysts to match the performance of new non PGM cathode catalysts.

4. Conclusions

The combination of XPS, HR-TEM/STEM and in-situ Raman spectroscopy has enabled us to elucidate the surface structure of the material formed during the synthesis. Using commercially available NiO nanopowder as seed for the growth of the precursor enables the formation of a catalyst powder rather than a metallic electrode with a thin coating. The catalyst is hence composed entirely of the active phase and facilitates the application of the catalyst, improving the contact between the gas diffusion layer and the membrane with the concomitant increase in activity of MEAs. As expected, the temperature of reductive annealing is an important factor in optimizing the activity. At $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the structure formed has a surface that is enriched in MoO_{3-x} and has increased roughness. The surface is characterized by agglomerated particles fused to the rod surface. In-situ Raman spectroscopy confirms the transformation from NiMoO_4 to MoO_{3-x} at high temperatures under H_2 . Electrochemical measurements demonstrate the improvement of performance compared to the analogous material prepared by the same procedure on Ni foam. A standard MEA of 5 cm^2 was then prepared and tested in an electrolyser cell using the MoO_{3-x} NiMoO_4 prepared at $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Stability test of 50 hours at 1 A cm^{-2} was carried out while monitoring the H_2 produced, with a cell voltage-based energy cost of $57.65 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2$. Lastly, scale-up water electrolysis cell was assembled, using an MEA of 78.5 cm^2 , this cell showed enhanced performance, reaching 0.9 A cm^2 at 1.8 V with an IrO_2 anode. When combined with a non PGM NiCo_2O_4 anode, 1 A cm^{-2} of electrolysis current density was produced at 2.0 V . In conclusion, we report a simple method to prepare a powder MoO_{3-x} NiMoO_4 catalyst that can be readily applied to electrode supports. Hence, scaling up of the catalyst synthesis and electrode preparation is facilitated, paving the way for the future application of such materials in larger AEM electrolyzers.

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